

Bringing GPU Support to Datashader

A RAPIDS Case Study

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Overview

- Datashader Overview
- Obstacles to GPU Acceleration
- Enter RAPIDS
- Performance Results
- Demo

Datashader Overview

Datashader is a high-performance Python library for generating a variety of principled visualizations of large datasets

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Datashader is a high-performance Python library for generating a **variety of** principled **visualizations** of large datasets

- Data Visualizations
 - Points
 - Lines
 - Meshes
 - Networks

Visualization of 300 million data points
(one per person in the USA) from the 2010 census¹

[1] examples.pyviz.org/census/census.html

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OpenSky flight dataset with over 10 million coordinates:
Ascending (Blue) vs. descending flights (Red)²

Datashader Overview

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Depth of Chesapeake and Delaware Bays with over 1 million triangles³

Datashader Overview

Datashader is a high-performance Python library for generating a **variety of** principled **visualizations** of large datasets

- Data Visualizations
 - Points
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Graph of research institutions linked by joint UK grants with over 600k edges⁴

Datashader Overview

Datashader is a **high-performance Python library** for generating a variety of principled visualizations of large datasets

- High-Performance Python
 - Data Structures
 - **NumPy**
 - **pandas**
 - **xarray**
 - Custom algorithms
 - **Numba**

Datashader Overview

Datashader is a high-performance Python library for generating a variety of **principled** visualizations of large datasets

Datashader Pipeline⁵

Datashader Integrations

HoloViews

Working with large data using datashader⁶

Dash

Making a Plotly Dash Census Viz Powered by RAPIDS⁷

[6] holoviews.org/user_guide/Large_Data.html

[7] medium.com/rapids-ai/plotly-census-viz-dashboard-powered-by-rapids-1503b3506652

Obstacles to GPU Acceleration

Obstacles to GPU Acceleration

Data Transfer

- Inputs must be copied from CPU to GPU memory
- Outputs must be copied from GPU back to CPU memory
- Large transfers for a fast operation reduces GPU speedup

GPU and CPU memory connection over PCIe⁸

Obstacles to GPU Acceleration

Code Reuse

- Traditional GPU programming is done in C, C++, or Fortran
- Datashader's core algorithms are written in Python, pandas, NumPy, and Numba
- Duplicating algorithms across languages is not sustainable

C++ CUDA

```
__global__  
void increment_by_one(int n, float *an_array)  
{  
    int index = threadIdx.x +  
                blockIdx.x * blockDim.x;  
    int stride = blockDim.x * gridDim.x;  
    for (int i = index; i < n; i += stride)  
        an_array[i] += 1;  
}
```

Python

```
def increment_by_one(an_array):  
    for i in range(an_array.size):  
        an_array[i] += 1
```

Enter RAPIDS (* and friends)

- **cuDF** (Pandas style DataFrames)
- **cuML** (Scikit-Learn style Machine Learning)
- **cuGraph** (NetworkX style graph analysis)
- **CuPy*** (numpy style N-dimensional arrays)
- **Numba for CUDA*** (Python to CUDA Just-in-time compiler)

Avoid Data Transfer with cuDF and CuPy

The RAPIDS ecosystem solves the data transfer problem by enabling the execution of entire data-processing, analysis, and visualization pipelines on the GPU

RAPIDS architecture⁹

Code Reuse with RAPIDS

The RAPIDS ecosystem makes it possible to implement domain logic in Python, and share it across CPU and GPU code paths

Code Reuse with RAPIDS

DataFrame

- pandas and cuDF

Shared Python domain function

```
def filter_sum(df, filter_col, filter_val, sum_col):  
    filtered_df = df[df[filter_col] == filter_val]  
    return filtered_df[sum_col].sum()
```

N-dimensional Array

- numpy and CuPy

Execute on CPU with pandas

```
import pandas as pd  
df = pd.read_csv("/path/to/receipts.csv")  
result = filter_sum(df, 'category', 'food', 'total')
```

Custom Algorithms

- Numba and Numba for CUDA

Execute on GPU with cuDF

```
import cudf  
df = cudf.read_csv("/path/to/receipts.csv")  
result = filter_sum(df, 'category', 'food', 'total')
```

Example: 1D Histogram

Code Reuse with RAPIDS

DataFrame

- pandas and cuDF

N-dimensional Array

- numpy and CuPy

Custom Algorithms

- Numba and Numba for CUDA

Example: 1D Histogram

Shared Python domain function

```
def zscore_normalize(feature):  
    shift = feature.mean(axis=0, keepdims=True)  
    scale = feature.std(axis=0, keepdims=True)  
    return (feature - shift) / scale
```

Execute on CPU with numpy

```
import numpy as np  
feature = np.random.rand(50, 100)  
normalized_feature = zscore_normalize(feature)
```

Execute on GPU with CuPy

```
import cupy  
feature = cupy.random.rand(50, 100)  
normalized_feature = zscore_normalize(feature)
```

Code Reuse with RAPIDS

DataFrame

- pandas and cuDF

N-dimensional Array

- numpy and CuPy

Custom Algorithms

- Numba and Numba for CUDA

Example: 1D Histogram

Shared element-wise domain function

```
@numba.jit
def increment_element_by_one(an_array, i):
    an_array[i] += 1
```

JIT-compile and execute on CPU

```
@numba.jit
def increment_by_one_cpu(an_array):
    for i in range(len(an_array)):
        increment_element_by_one(an_array, i)
```

JIT-compile and execute on GPU

```
@numba.cuda.jit
def increment_by_one_gpu(an_array):
    i = numba.cuda.grid(1)
    if i < an_array.size:
        increment_element_by_one(an_array, i)
```

Code Reuse with RAPIDS

DataFrame

- pandas and cuDF

N-dimensional Array

- numpy and CuPy

Custom Algorithms

- Numba and Numba for CUDA

Example: 1D Histogram

Full Example Notebook

CPU / GPU code reuse example: 1D Histogram

This notebook contains a minimal example of the approach that Datashader uses to share the implementation of custom algorithms between CPU and GPU code paths using numba.

The example is a 1D histogram implementation with `count`, `min`, and `max` aggregation functions

Imports / constants

```
In [1]: import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from math import isnan
from numba import jit, cuda
import cupy
import cudf
from toolz import memoize

ngjit = jit(nopython=True, nogil=True)
```

Define CPU Aggregation functions. These will be executed serially, so there are no race conditions to worry about.

CPU/GPU code reuse example: 1D Histogram¹⁰

Datashader Performance Results

Points

~10x speedups for Points / Lines rendering¹¹

300 million data points
(one per person in the USA) from the 2010 census

QuadMesh

5x-120x speedup for QuadMesh rendering¹²

Synthetic QuadMesh pattern

[11] anaconda.org/jonmmease/datashader-rapids-census/notebook

[12] anaconda.org/jonmmease/datashader-rapids-quadmash/notebook

Dash+RAPIDS+Datashader Example

Draft Screencast prepared by RAPIDS team

References

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